

TMGWO: A HYBRID FEATURE SELECTION METHOD FOR MACHINE LEARNING IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract

Timely identification and characterization play a pivotal role in the management of chronic renal disease. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major burden on the healthcare system due to the growing number of patients, the increased risk of progression to end-stage renal disease, and the dismal prognosis in terms of morbidity and death. Early detection of CKD is critical to saving many lives. This study is unique in that it developed a diagnostic system that uses a hybrid feature selection strategy in conjunction with different Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to identify CKD. The University of California, Irvine (UCI) Machine Learning repository provided 400 clinical records of patients with CKD that were used in the study. The dataset was prepared for the prediction model using a variety of methods, such as encoding categorical features, imputing missing values, removing outlier factors, normalizing data, and choosing relevant features. To get rid of irrelevant features, a hybrid strategy that combines the two-phase mutation grey wolf optimization (TMGWO) was suggested for feature selection. A Pearson correlation matrix was also calculated in order to determine which features were most important for prediction. In the end, the Extra Trees classifier showed an astounding 98% accuracy in CKD diagnosis, with no data leakage and a 2% true negative rate across 14 machine learning models. In contrast, the Bagging classifier performed the worst, achieving an accuracy rate of just 60%.

Keywords—chronic kidney disease (CKD), grey wolf optimization, TMGWO, Machine Learning, Deep Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the body's most important organs, the kidney, filters and removes metabolic waste products from blood plasma before excreting them through urine. Apart from its basic function, the kidney also plays a vital role in controlling the synthesis of red blood cells by regulating pH levels, producing and releasing hormones that control blood pressure, maintaining the body's fluid and electrolyte balance, and synthesizing an active form of vitamin D to support strong and healthy bones[1]. CKD can be effectively managed in its early stages but, in its advanced stages, leads to kidney failure if untreated. Considering its significant effect on death, CKD is a kidney disease that can be managed in its early stages before reaching the point of renal failure. CKD has attracted a lot of attention because of its high death rate. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), chronic illnesses are now a serious threat to developing countries[2].

Seven hundred fifty three (753) million people globally, 336 million men and 417 million women, lost their lives to CKD in 2016 [3]. It is classified as a "chronic" illness because of its slow onset and long-lasting effects on the urinary system. Risk factors for cardiovascular disease (CVD), diabetes, and high blood pressure are common in patients with CKD[4]. Patients in underdeveloped nations may progress to the final phases, necessitating kidney transplantation or dialysis. The glomerular filtration rate,

or GFR, is used by medical professionals to evaluate kidney function and identify renal disease. GFR is calculated by considering a number of variables, including the patient's age, gender, blood test results, and other pertinent information. Doctors can divide CKD into five stages based on the GFR value. If kidney failure is detected and treated early, it is frequently preventable from progressing to kidney failure. The stages of renal disease as indicated by GFR are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 The CKD development phases

Description	GFR	Stage
Kidneys working normally	≥ 90	1
Minor damage to the kidney	60-89	2
Moderate damage to the kidney	30-59	3
Severe damage to the kidney	12-29	4
Kidney Failure	≤ 15	5

Kidney failure can be avoided by detecting and treating chronic renal disease in its early stages. Early detection is the key to managing chronic kidney disease because waiting until it is too late to receive a diagnosis may result in kidney failure and the need for dialysis or kidney transplantation in order to lead a normal life. The standard medical diagnosis for chronic kidney disease is a urine albumin test or a blood test to measure glomerular filtration.

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There is an urgent need for computer-assisted diagnostics to help doctors and radiologists make accurate diagnostic decisions because of the rising number of people with chronic renal conditions, the lack of specialized medical professionals, and the high costs of diagnosis and treatment, especially in developing countries.

Recent developments in data analysis and predictive modeling include machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). ML model uses data, algorithms, and statistical methods to be trained to make predictions and classify things. When used in the healthcare industry, the model can help avoid unfavorable outcomes like the need for dialysis or transplantation by predicting in advance whether a patient is at risk of developing CKD. It can also facilitate early preventive measures and offer more effective therapies.

Figure 1 Factors affecting chronic kidney disease.

Diabetes, heart disease, high blood pressure, certain diets, and a family history of medical conditions can all have a detrimental effect on kidney function and hasten the emergence of CKD. A visual depiction of some of these significant variables in relation to chronic kidney disease is shown in Figure 1.

This paper significantly advances the field by presenting two phase mutation grey wolf optimization (TMGWO), a hybrid feature selection method. This method has been used to successfully identify cases of CKD and non-CKD cases using 14 different ML algorithms. Crucially, this approach can be expanded upon and utilized for diagnosing analogous medical conditions on other health datasets.

When combined with the hybrid feature selection technique, the Extra Trees classifier outperformed the other algorithms, according to test results and comparisons with pertinent studies. This highlights the possibility for broader applicability in the field of healthcare data analysis and demonstrates its superior performance in the task of CKD detection.

2. LITERATURE

Various studies have used different classification algorithms to predict the stages of CKD. Using a dataset of clinical test results from 817 patients at Birdem Hospital in Dhaka over a two-year period (2011–2013), Ahmed et al.[5] designed a fuzzy-based intelligent system

to evaluate the urinary system, achieving an accuracy rate of 86.7%.

Khamparia et al.[6] presented a deep-stacked autoencoder model for CKD detection in a different study. With 250 CKD cases and 150 non-CKD cases in the UCI machine learning database, this model was trained, resulting in an astounding 100% accuracy and 100% specificity.

A genetic algorithm (GA) based on neural networks (NN) was presented by Kim et al.[7] to aid in the diagnosis of CKD. In order to improve NN training, their GA methodology concentrated on optimizing weight vectors. The 741 ultrasound images in the dataset used in the study included 251 images of healthy kidneys, 328 images of kidneys with mild to moderate CKD, and 162 images of kidneys with severe CKD. The researchers' remarkable classification rate of 95.4% was attained by using an artificial neural network (ANN). Al Mansour et al.[8] sought to identify CKD in its early stages through their study. The 400-patient dataset that the authors used for their classification techniques contained 24 parameters that were pertinent to the diagnosis of this condition. The researchers used support vector machines (SVM) and ANN to diagnose CKD. Impressive accuracy of 99.75% for ANN and 97.75% for SVM was shown by their results.

Rady et al.[9] used a variety of techniques in their CKD dataset diagnosis study, including SVM, Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Radial Basis Functions (RBF), and Probabilistic Neural Networks ("PNN"). With an accuracy rate of 96.7%, the authors discovered that the SVM, MLP, and RBF algorithms performed better than the PNN approach.

In order to enhance the diagnosis of CKD, Wibawa et al.[10] used AdaBoost for ensemble learning and correlation-based feature selection (CFS) for feature selection. Their method combined K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) with CFS and AdaBoost to achieve the highest accuracy of 98.1%. For their study, the researchers used 400 instances from the UCI machine learning repository.

Chiu et al.[11] developed intelligent models for the classification of CKD that included neural network techniques. These models, which included Generalized Feed-Forward Neural Networks (GRNN), Back-Propagation Networks (BPN), and Modular Neural Networks (MNN), were designed to aid in the early diagnosis of CKD. In addition, the authors presented hybrid models that combined the previously mentioned neural network models with GA.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section discusses the various methodologies and materials used in this study. The methodologies for preparing datasets, the hybrid feature selection methodology, and the various ML algorithms used to diagnose are described and analyzed. The primary goal of this study was to examine the CKD dataset; thus, 14 ML algorithms were used: Ada Boost Classifier, Bagging Classifier, CatBoost Classifier, Decision Tree Classifier, Extra Trees Classifier, Gaussian Naive Bayes (Gaussian NB), Gradient Boosting Classifier, K- nearest neighbors, LightGBM Classifier, MLP, Random Forest Classifier, Stochastic Gradient Class. Missing numerical values were calculated using the Min-Max Scaler and the Imputed K-

Nearest Neighbor approach. The most significant characteristics are then identified using a hybrid feature selection approach called TMGWO. Following that, the dataset values are standardized using the Standard Scalar technique, and the ML Models are trained. In this work,

the K-fold cross-validation strategy is used for validation, and ultimately, the training data are encoded using the One-hot-encoding technique. The workflow of the suggested methodology for CKD diagnosis is depicted in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 Proposed Methodology

Dataset preparation

The CKD dataset used in this investigation was obtained from the University of California, Irvine Machine Learning Repository, which contained data on 400 patients with chronic kidney disease. In addition to class features such as "CKD" and "not-CKD," the dataset contains 24 variables divided into 11 numeric characteristics and 13 category features for classification. The diagnostic class has two values: "CKD" and "not-CKD". Table 2 depicts an overview of the dataset properties. To prepare the dataset for the model, various data preprocessing approaches were used.

Initially, the duplicate sample checker was used to prevent data leaking, and no duplicate sample was discovered in the dataset. The cross-validation and testing approach was then used to separate 70% of the data for training and 30% for testing. In the following phase, data preparation algorithms based purely on the training set were devised and applied for both partitions. While cleaning the dataset, 10 categorical (nominal) features were discovered, and these features were encoded into 0's or 1's with the help of the One-hot-encoding technique. The working technique of the One-hot-encoding method is highlighted in Eq. (1). It is a conventional base vector for e_i , where e_i represents the vector with a 1 in the i th coordinate and 0's elsewhere.

$$e_i = 1_A := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Table 2 CKD dataset downloaded from UCI machine learning repository

Dataset characteristics	Multivariate
Data source	UCI ML repository
Number of CKD classes	250
Number of not CKD classes	150
Number of features	26
Number of instances	400

The dataset's features or characteristics contain 24 distinct features and 1 binary classification attribute. The Pearson correlation matrix of the dataset used is shown in Fig. 4.

By comparing and separating samples, normalization improves ML models' ability to discover patterns in data. Surprisingly, the dataset has a number of missing values that must be imputed. Because of its working principle that focuses on working by measuring distances, this study used KNN imputation approaches for the imputation. Direct imputation based on raw data, on the other hand, may be incorrect. The Min-Max Scaler method was used to further rescale the features[12]. Using the following equation (2), it rescales the feature range from 0 to 1. In the equation, X represents the true values, while X_{min} min and X_{max} max represent the minimum and maximum values of the feature f_i .

$$X_V = \frac{x - X_{min}}{X_{max} - X_{min}} \quad (2)$$

As the dataset contains 1008 missing values from 24 features and 400 records, this research used KNN

imputation techniques in the next step to manage the missing values. The mean value of the k-neighbors found in the data set is used to impute the missing values of each sample. The KNN Imputation technique takes $k = 8$ into account and assumes uniform weight.

Some of the features in the distribution have quite far outliers. Three characteristics are handled as continuous values in this case because they are measures of biological variables that operate as continuous in reality. However, some features contain a substantial fraction of missing data; consequently, measures of central tendency cannot be imputed and would distort their distributions.

Feature Selection

According to Qin et al.[13], identifying the most significant risk variables in healthcare informatics aids in the elimination of redundant features, the improvement of data consistency, the reduction of ML algorithm training time, and the improvement of prediction performance. As a result, many methods for selecting qualities or eliminating less relevant aspects have gained popularity over time. Researchers have employed a range of procedures to choose relevant features in recent years, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Chi-squared (Chi2) Test, Mutual Information (MI), and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE).

The Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) is a modern meta-heuristic approach that was developed by Mirjalili and associates [14] and is modeled after the behavior of grey wolves. The GWO algorithm's approach to search agent movement is akin to the hunting process and leadership structure of grey wolves [15]. The GWO algorithm was used for this investigation because numerous research studies have consistently shown it to perform better.

The best names to use when describing the grey wolf pack's leadership hierarchy are alpha (α), followed by beta (β) and delta (δ), with omega (ω) coming last. The optimization model that will be created will be modeled by the hunting habits of grey wolves, with omega trailing closely behind and alpha, beta, and delta leading the way. At time $t = 1$, the iteration starts when prey is found. The omega wolves are then led by the alpha, beta, and delta wolf packs to locate and eventually encircle the prey. Three coefficients are introduced to explain the encircling behavior: α , β , and δ .

More details about the standard grey wolf optimization is found in [14]. An improved version of the standard grey wolf optimization is TMGWO [16]. Key steps in the TMGWO process are initialization, assessment, application of the transformation function, and a two-phase mutation. In the subsections that follow, each of these phases will be thoroughly explained.

Initialization

The first step, called initialization, is to produce a population of search agents or wolves at random. Every search agent is a possible fix and has a dimension equal to the total number of features in the initial dataset. Each solution in this feature selection issue is tasked with selecting a subset of characteristics that will optimize classification accuracy, for example, if the dataset comprises 10 features, as shown in Fig. 3. It means

assigning a value of "1" to specific qualities in order to include them and rejecting others with a value of "0." All solutions are first set up with binary values (0 or 1). Figure 3 shows the representation of the solutions.

1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
1	2	...						d	

Figure 3 Representation of solution

Evaluation

A problem is classified as multi-objective when it has numerous objectives that need to be satisfied at the same time in order to find the best solution. This is a multi-objective problem in the context of feature selection since it requires achieving two competing objectives:

1. Reducing the number of features that are chosen.
2. Optimizing a given classifier's classification accuracy.

The fitness function for evaluating the solutions is carefully designed to balance these two aims in light of these goals.

$$fitness = \alpha y_R(D) + \beta \frac{|S|}{|D|} \quad (3)$$

Where $y_R(D)$ denotes the classification error rate for the condition attribute set R in relation to the decision D. This rate is determined through the use of the K-nearest neighbors (KNN) classifier, as originally described by [17].

The symbol N represents the size of the selected feature subset.

Meanwhile, M signifies the total count of features present in each sample within the original dataset.

The parameters α and β are employed as weighting factors to denote the significance of classification accuracy and the length of the selected feature subset. These parameters adhere to the range $\alpha [0,1]$, with β being expressed as $1 - \alpha$. Classification accuracy is given more weight than the number of features that are chosen. If the assessment function only considers classification accuracy, it may unintentionally ignore solutions with comparable accuracy but fewer chosen characteristics. These characteristics are essential for solving the dimensionality issue. Based on the majority of its K nearest neighbors, each sample in the KNN context can be given to a certain class label. The KNN classifier has a reputation for being easily implemented. Classifying newly incoming samples for which the class name is unknown is the fundamental task of classification.

Transformation function

In a conventional GWO, the positions of the search agents provide continuous values. Consequently, the binary character of feature selection makes its direct applicability to our situation difficult. This problem stems from the fundamental decision of feature selection, which is determining which features to select (1) or not select (0) in order to maximize classification accuracy. In order to close this gap, a transformation function is presented, which transforms the typical GWO's continuous search space into a binary one. In this case, two different

transformation functions are used. First, we have the sigmoidal function, which is identified as an example of an S-shaped function[18]. The second function is called the tanh function[19] described it in detail as an example of a V-shaped function. The sigmoidal and tanh functions can both transform continuous values into binary values by use of the subsequent procedure:

$$x_{s_i} = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x_t}}, x_{binary} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } rand < x_{s_i} \\ 1 & \text{if } rand \geq x_{s_i} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$x_{t_i} = |\tanh(x)|, x_{binary} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } rand < x_{v_i} \\ 1 & \text{if } rand \geq x_{v_i} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Both x_{s_i} and x_{v_i} stand for continuous characteristics when used in the context of a search agent. These characteristics line up with the V- and S-shaped functions, respectively. There is also a binary value, which has two possible values: 0 and 1. The continuous feature values and a randomly generated number are compared to determine this binary value. These two functions are primarily meant to convert the continuous search space into a binary representation.

Two phase mutations

To enhance the efficiency of the suggested algorithm, a two-phase mutation operator is utilized. The first stage of mutation seeks to minimize the number of selected features while preserving a high degree of classification precision. The next stage is about adding more informative elements to improve the categorization precision.

4. MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS

In order to develop novel and understandable patterns, data mining approaches were used to generate categorization templates [20]. Both supervised and unsupervised learning methodologies used in clinical and medical diagnostics for regression and classification need the construction of models based on historical analysis.

K-Nearest Neighbor

The goal of this technique is to cluster objects that are near to one another. It makes use of feature vectors and class labels from a dataset, as explained in [21]. The KNN method uses a similarity metric to help categorize new examples while keeping track of all previous ones. Text is represented as a spatial vector $S = S(T_1, W_1; T_2, W_2; \dots T_n, W_n2;)$ in the K-NN's representation. The training text is used to calculate its similarity to any other text, and the texts that score highest on similarity are chosen. Lastly, class assignments are created using K neighbors.

Random Forest This algorithm produces a large collaborative ensemble of decision trees. Decision trees serve as the foundation of this method. According to [22], a "random forest" is a collection of decision trees whose nodes were created during the preprocessing stage. A random subset of features is used to determine the best feature after multiple trees have been constructed. The development of decision trees, which are a component of random forests, is another idea that results from the decision tree algorithm. These trees are used to categorize new objects based on an input vector. Data classification is the responsibility of each individual decision tree. The random forest then chooses the classification with the

highest vote count among all the trees in the forest, assuming votes are assigned to particular classes. Figure 4. The Pearson correlation matrix is employed to represent features within the dataset.

Support Vector Machine

In machine learning, supervised learning models called SVMs are used to examine data and find patterns. According to [23], the basic SVM is a non-probabilistic binary linear classifier that analyzes input data and predicts the output class by choosing one of two potential classes. Using individual training examples labeled as belonging to one of these two categories, SVM training creates a model that classifies incoming instances into one of two groups.

In addition to doing linear classification, SVMs may also efficiently execute non-linear classification by an implicit mapping of inputs into high-dimensional feature spaces, a method called the kernel method.

GaussianNB classifier

The Naive Bayes (NB) classifier outperforms more intricate classification techniques that depend on the assumption of the existence of a particular class when no similar characteristics are present. According to [24] study, the NB classifier is built using Bayes' theorem and depends on conditional probability. This classifier's excellent efficiency with huge datasets and capacity to produce insightful results make it useful as a supervised ML technique in the study of medical statistics data.

Decision tree classifier

A decision tree (DT) is a structure in which nodes represent input qualities, and the output is generated by projecting the outcome based on the information gathered about the height of that specific feature. Subtrees are generated by merging attributes that were not used in previous steps. Internal nodes of a decision tree represent input variables, branches represent outcomes, and leaf nodes represent classes [25]. The tree has numerous layers of nodes, with the root node at the top and the leaves at the bottom.

Multi-layer perceptron (MLP)

The MLP is a neural network that generates a unique vector for each set of inputs. The multilayered perceptron structure of the MLP consists of an output layer, an input layer, and hidden layers.

Bagging Classifier

Bagging is a technique for enhancing the performance of machine learning classification systems. This strategy, invented by Leo Breiman and dubbed "bootstrap aggregating" [26], entails building a classification algorithm that creates a classifier $H: D \rightarrow \{1, -1\}$ for binary classification using a training set of sample descriptions D . In response to fluctuations in the training set, the bagging technique generates a series of classifiers H_m , where $m = 1, \dots, M$. When these classifiers are combined, a composite classifier is formed.

Gradient boosting classifier

The basic concept underlying gradient boosting is to use the boosting process to optimize a set of cost functions. To

improve the classifier, the gradient descent paths for minimizing the loss function are translated into successively acquired decision trees [27]. Gradient boosting's goal is to learn a function F from a set of

plausible hypotheses H while minimizing the predicted loss over the distribution D . This is accomplished by the use of a training dataset in which each data point (x, y) follows the distribution D .

Figure 4 The Pearson correlation matrix is employed to represent features within the dataset

AdaBoost classifier

The AdaBoost approach was used in this study to build a robust classifier using a training strategy known as weak learning. The goal of weak learning was to find the classifier that best discriminated between positive and negative samples. It entailed calculating the best threshold value for each feature in order to reduce the number of misclassified cases[28].

CatBoost classifier

The CatBoost classifier is another ML algorithm for predicting category features. It makes use of a gradient boosting method using binary decision trees as primary predictors[29]. Consider a dataset of $D = (X_j, y_j) j = 1, \dots, m$ samples, where $X_j = (x_{1j}, x_{2j}, \dots, x_{nj})$ is a vector of n qualities and $y_j \in R$ is a binary (yes or no) or numerical feature (0 or 1). The samples (X_j, y_j) are distributed independently and identically according to an unknown distribution $p(.,.)$.

Extra trees classifier

The Extra-Trees technique builds an ensemble of unpruned decision or regression trees using the traditional top-down approach. It varies from earlier tree-based ensemble techniques in two ways: it divides nodes randomly and generates trees using the complete learning sample rather than a bootstrap replica [30]. The extra-trees

splitting procedure for numerical attributes is described in procedure 1, which includes two parameters: T , which represents the number of randomly picked characteristics at each node, and $pmin$, which represents the minimum sample size for node splitting. The tree forecasts are aggregated to provide the final prediction, which is determined by a majority vote in classification tasks and an arithmetic average in regression problems. The Split_node (E) function carries out the node splitting operation, and the function

pick_random_split (E, b) yields the split value. The final result is obtained through the Stop_split (E) function.

LightGBM classifier

LightGBM, a scalable tree boosting engine, was introduced by Chen et al.[31]. While XGBoost had outstanding accuracy, the LightGBM ensemble was more robust, computationally economical, and time-efficient[32].

XGBoost classifier

Extreme Gradient Boosting is a boosted tree technique that is based on the concept of gradient boosting [33]. XGBoost differs from previous gradient boosting algorithms in that it uses a more regularized model formulation to reduce data overfitting, resulting in improved performance.

5. EXPERIMENTAL CONFIGURATION AND DISCUSSION

All of our tests were carried out using the 64-bit version of Windows 10 Ultimate, an Intel Core i5-3317U CPU running at 1.70 GHz, and four gigabytes of RAM. We implemented our work using Python programming language. The experimentation entailed the utilization of various contexts, with Table 3 outlining the necessary setup. All procedures were carried out on a local PC using Python's Jupyter Notebook and libraries or modules such as Scikit Learn, NumPy, Pandas, Seaborn, and Matplotlib. Furthermore, different evaluation metrics were employed to evaluate the performance of the available ML classifier.

Table 3 System Specifications for the Machine Learning Model Development

RAM	16GB
CPU	1 × single core hyper threaded; Xeon processors @2.3GHz
Cache	46MB
GPU	NVidia K80 GPU
GPU Memory	16GB
Session Limit	10 h
Disk Space	100GB

The following Eqs. present the procedure of calculating other evaluation metrics of the Confusion Matrix. Accuracy (AC), Precision (P), Recall (R), and F1-score are calculated by calculating successfully categorized samples (TP and TN) as well as mistakenly classified samples (FP and FN).

$$AC = \frac{TN + TP}{TN + TP + FN + FP} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TN + TP + FN + FP} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

$$F1 \text{ score} = \frac{2 \times P \times R}{P + R} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

The accuracy attained in detecting CKD and non-CKD classes based on the dataset is depicted in Fig. 5, with a 70% training data and 30% test data split for experimentation. Table 4 also calculates and displays precision, recall, and F1-score. The Extra Trees model obtains the greatest accuracy of 98% among the 14 machine learning classifiers, along with 99% precision, 98% recall, and 98% F1-score. The Extra Trees classifier classifies 60% of 120 (30%) test results as non-CKD and 40% as CKD. The Extra Trees classifier effectively identified True Positive samples with 98% accuracy, resulting in a 2% error rate. In comparison, Ada Boost, Random Forest, and SVM achieved accuracies of 98%, 97%, and 98% in recognizing positive samples, with error rates of 2%, 3%, and 2%, respectively. Following closely behind Ada Boost, Random Forest, and SVM, CatBoost and XGBoost achieved an accuracy of 96%, with each having a true negative rate of 5%. Following that, XGBoost and the Decision Tree classifier achieved 95% and 94% accuracy, respectively, with 95% and 94% true positive sample detection rates.

Gaussian NB and Stochastic Gradient Boosting tied for fifth place in maximum accuracy, both with 93%. However, they differ in terms of precision, recall, and F1-score. Gaussian NB achieved 93% precision, recall, and

F1-score, while Stochastic Gradient Boosting achieved 94%, 92%, and 93%, respectively.

On the dataset, the Backpropagation-based multi-layer perceptron architecture was also tested, providing less than 90% accuracy with comparable precision, recall, and F1-score values.

Surprisingly, the KNN and Bagging classifiers had the lowest accuracy, with 67% and 60%, respectively, and error rates of 23% and 50%, respectively.

Table 4 Performance metrics of the machine learning model across the dataset.

ML Classifier	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Ada Boost Classifier	98%	96%	97%
Bagging Classifier	30%	50%	37%
CatBoost Classifier	96%	95%	96%
Decision Tree Classifier	94%	93%	94%
Extra Trees Classifier	98%	97%	98%
Gaussian Naive Bayes (Gaussian NB)	93%	93%	93%
Gradient Boosting Classifier	95%	88%	93%
K-nearest neighbors	66%	67%	66%
LightGBM Classifier	95%	96%	95%
Multi-Layer Perceptron	89%	89%	89%
Random Forest Classifier	97%	96%	96%
Stochastic Gradient Boosting	94%	92%	93%
Support vector machines (SVM)	98%	97%	97%
XGBoost	95%	94%	95%

In conclusion, the Extra Trees Classifier had the best accuracy (98%), whereas the Bagging Classifier had the lowest accuracy (60%). CKD is a long-term illness characterized by impaired kidney function that has a major impact on the quality of life of those affected. CKD has a significant cost impact on patients, healthcare providers, and the government. Renal replacement therapy (RRT) for end-stage renal disease (ESRD) is both costly and time-consuming. Patients with ESRD frequently require hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, or, in some situations, transplantation. Predicting trends in CKD prevalence is critical from a public health standpoint. This allows decision-makers, such as ministries, insurers, and hospital administrators, to put in place suitable safeguards to avoid an increase in the number of patients. Machine-learning algorithms based on biomedical laboratory data are increasingly being used in healthcare to develop disease prediction models. In this work, the Extra Trees classifier outperformed 14 traditional machine learning models in terms of accuracy and other performance measures on the Chronic Kidney Dataset, which is available at the UCI Machine Learning repository.

This study also looked at the Extra Trees classifier's complexity values, revealing that the time complexity of building an Extra-Trees model is $O(v \cdot n \log(n))$, where v represents the number of attributes and n represents the number of records. The findings of this study have important consequences, especially as the Extra Trees classifier is not often used as a predictor in health informatics. Despite the fact that KNN, Decision Tree, SVM, and Random Forest frequently outperform others in CKD diagnosis performance measures, this study highlighted the use of a hybrid feature selection technique. Notably, whereas other previous studies used the Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) technique, this study took a different strategy.

Figure 5 Classification accuracy percentage for all classifiers

This study also included stepwise data preparation processes, with the hybrid TMGWO feature selection method used to reconstruct the dataset for model use. Encoding, normalization, missing value imputation, outlier elimination, imbalance handling, feature selection, and standardization were all part of the data preparation procedure. These methods contributed to an overall accuracy of over 90% across 12 separate machine learning models, and an accuracy of over 60% from the remaining two models using the top 85% (13) linked features. As a result, the accuracy range in this study ranges from 98% to 60%. The suggested model was tested using a single dataset of 24 features from 400 patients. Table 5 compares and analyzes the proposed system with existing approaches. According to the comparative Table 5, several previous studies obtained somewhat higher accuracy than the suggested approach, but only a few studies evaluated CKD data using a feature selection approach, notably Recursive Feature Elimination. Notably, no previous research offered a reproducible hybrid wrapper feature selection approach applicable to comparable health datasets for identifying comparable disorders. Furthermore, the importance of selecting relevant and significant features is emphasized, potentially leading to improved diagnostic accuracy with a lower mistake rate.

Table 5 Comparative analysis of the performance of the proposed model with previous studies

Reference	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Ahmed et al. [5]	86.7%	-	-	-
Khamparia et al. [6]	100%	100%	100%	100%
Kim et al. [7]	95.4%	-	-	-
Almansour et al. [8]	99.75%	100%	99.6%	99.7%
Rady et al. [9]	96.70%	98.75%	100%	99.37%
Kunwar et al. [34]	100%	-	-	-
Wibawa et al. [10]	98.10%	98.10%	98.0%	98.0%
Avcı et al. [35]	99%	98%	99%	98%
Chiu et al. [11]	91.71%	-	-	-
Sara et al. [36]	90%	95.24%	90.91%	93.02%
Senan et al. [37]	100%	100%	100%	100%
Krishnamurthy et al. [38]	90%	78%	88.2%	78.1%
Our proposed (TMGWO + Extra Trees)	98%	97%	98%	99%

Extra-Trees splitting algorithm

Split_node(E)

Input: E, the local learning subset corresponding to the split node

Output: nothing or a split $[b < bc]$

- if stop_split(E) is true return nothing
- else

Select T attributes $\{b1, b2, \dots, bT\}$ among all candidate attributes that are not constant (in E);

- Draw T splits $\{e1, e2, \dots, eT\}$, $ei = \text{pick_random_split}(E, bi)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, T$
- Return e^* when $\text{Score}(e^*, E) = \max_{i=1, 2, \dots, T} \text{Score}(ei, E)$

pick_random_split(E, b)

Inputs: attribute b and subset (E)

Output: a split

- Let the minimal and maximum value of b in E are $bEmin$, $bEmax$, respectively.

- Uniformly in $[bEmin, bEmax]$ a random cut-point (bc) is drawn.

- Return the split $[b < bc]$

Stop_split (E)

Input: a subset (E)

Output: 0 or 1 (Boolean)

- If $|E| < pmin$

Return True

- If all of E's attributes are constant,

Return True

- If the output in E is constant,

Return True

- Else

Return False

6. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the ability of machine learning algorithms to detect CKD using a small number of tests or characteristics. Several machine learning algorithms were used to detect CKD at an early stage, including Ada Boost, Bagging classifier, CatBoost, Decision Tree, Extra Trees, Gaussian Nave Bayes, K-nearest neighbor, Gradient Boosting, LightGBM, Multi-Layer Perceptron, Random Forest, Stochastic Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Machine, and XGBoost. The complete dataset was subjected to a hybrid wrapper feature selection approach TMGWO, in which the most influential features were chosen for predicting CKD based on correlation scores. The suggested hybrid feature selection strategy outperformed existing algorithms, particularly when combined with the Extra Trees classifier, achieving a better accuracy score. The findings of this study imply that machine learning-based models can be useful for resource creation and supporting public health programs such as patient monitoring and early detection of CKD. In terms of future plans, it is planned to create a web application that will aid clinicians in the real-time detection of kidney failure patients. There are also plans to collect a dataset of ultrasound images of CKD patients and investigate the use of deep learning approaches for CKD screening.

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